

VISIBLE INTEGRAL FIELD UNITS SUCH AS MUSE

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VISIBLE INTEGRAL FIELD UNITS SUCH AS MUSE

Outline:

	1st generation, 4+8m	2nd generation, 8m	3rd generation, ELT
Introduction			
Flat Field Calibration			
Line Spread Function			
Summary, Outlook			

(1) Introduction

Integral Field Units, Principle of Operation

Potential for 3D-Spectrophotometry!

Slit spectrographs : effects of slit illumination and centering of point sources

Bacon et al. 1995, A&ASuppl. 113, 347

Potsdam Multiaperture Spectrophotometer

Roth et al. 2005, PASP 117, 620
Kelz et al. 2006, PASP 118, 129

PSF-fitting crowded field 3D spectroscopy with PMAS

Modelling the Point Spread Function (PSF):

$$\hat{x} = (x - x^n) \cos \theta - (y - y^n) \sin \theta,$$

$$\hat{y} = (x - x^n) \sin \theta + (y - y^n) \cos \theta,$$

$$r(x, y) = \sqrt{\hat{x}^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{y}}{1 - e}\right)^2}$$

$$M(x, y) = \Sigma_0 \left(1 + \left(\frac{r(x, y)}{r_d} \right)^2 \right)^{-\beta}$$

$$FWHM = 2 \sqrt{2^{1/\beta} - 1} r_d$$

Moffat Function

PSF-fitting crowded field 3D spectroscopy

PampelMuse ©

Modelling the Point Spread Function (PSF):

monochromatic maps

PSF-fitting crowded field 3D spectroscopy with PMAS

M3

HST image

PSF-fitting crowded field 3D spectroscopy at the VLT

VMOS IFU
(1.4" seeing)

Becker 2002

FLAMES IFU
(0.8" seeing)

Kamann et al. 2013

MUSE

NGC6397

Husser et al. 2016
A&A 588, A148

Kamann et al. 2016
A&A 588, A149

NGC6397

NGC6397

→ deblending spectra with PampelMuse

NGC 300
 $(m - M)_0 = 26.36$

IFU Spectrophotometry:

- no slit losses
- insensitive to pointing errors
- insensitive to differential atmospheric refraction
- enables blind pointing faint object spectroscopy
- enables PSF-fitting techniques à la CCD photometry
- ideal for emission line object (HII regions, PN, SNR,...)
- offers advantages for sky subtraction

however:

- requires accurate calibration of spaxel-to-spaxel throughput variations: flatfield correction
- significantly more complicated instrumental problem than for direct imaging

(2) Flat Field Calibration

Why is flatfield calibration more difficult for IFS than for direct imaging cameras?

- single datacube layer generally records fewer photons than a broadband (or even narrowband) image
 - datacube layer results from extracted and rebinned spectra: rebinning generates systematics
 - light path is generally more complex
 - risk of systematics like vignetting/scattered light/...
 - such systematics sensitively depend on the details of illumination → non-linear effects
- sky flat affected by absorption lines
- sky super-flat often not an option
- dome flat or internal flatfield screen less than optimal

MUSE Calibration Unit

VMOS IFU spaxel-to-spaxel response variation

VMOS IFU spaxel-to-spaxel response variation

IRAS 13031-571

VMOS IFU spaxel-to-spaxel response variation

PMAS raw spectra

Tracing and optimal extraction

<http://p3d.sourceforge.net/>

Sandin et al. 2010
Sandin et al. 2011

standard swath extraction:

Flux lost in the wings: ~10% on both sides

Contamination from adjacent spectra

Fiber sensitivity variation of order 20% → systematical extraction errors up to 9%.

optimal extraction: simultaneous weighted fit of all spectral profiles

Mapping scattered light:

MPFS flatfield

scattered light map

PMAS flat-field variation vs. telescope zenith distance

single spaxel transmission variation over 4 hrs,
tracking under real observing conditions

MUSE: field splitter and slicer

Fore-optics

Splitting optics

Relay optics

Slicer optics

CCD 4k²

VPHG

Camera f/2

Collimator

Slicer

Slicer optics

Image Dissector Array (IDA)

Focussing Mirror Array (FMA)

Pupil / Slit Mask

MUSE pipeline

MUSE: resampling and correlated noise

Layer of empty (sky only) datacube

associated STAT layer

MUSE: resampling and correlated noise

Experiment: Create pixtable with random data with zero mean and unit variance, resample into datacube (same geometry grid as real data), create STAT cube.

Reason: Adjacent cube pixels are not independent, covariances $\neq 0$.

Factor ~ 6 ratio in STAT for adjacent pixels (but same "true" σ^2 !)

MUSE flatfield systematics / superflat

After pipeline processing, there appears background substructure:

- varying slowly with wavelength
- stable over timescale of several months
- can be corrected by masked average of many frames („superflat“)
- remaining systematics typically $\pm 2\%$ of sky background

“Superflat” from 24 MUSE-
Wide fields

Continuum map of
standard flatfielded
science datacube

Continuum map of
superflat-corrected
science datacube

MUSE observation of 27 hours total exposure time in HDFs

Results:

- 189 redshifts to $I_{814}=29.5$
- 26 new LAE detected below WFCP2 detection limit
- 227 emission line objects
- 17 groups of galaxies
- kinematics of galaxies

(3) Line Spread Function

Knowledge of the LSF for all spaxels and wavelengths in the datacube is important for:

- wavelength calibration
- kinematics of galaxies: measuring velocity fields, σ , and higher moments
- stellar population synthesis
- radial velocities of stars, galaxies, nebulae,...
- OH sky emission line subtraction
- ...

Measurement of MUSE LSF

- Gaussian fit of 19 groups of skylines distributed the most uniformly possible along the wavelength range. The fit is performed on each spaxel of the cube before being averaged over the field of view.
- data: HDFS observation
- CAMEL software

Measurement of MUSE LSF – spatial variation 7055 Å

Measurement of MUSE LSF – spatial variation 4650 Å

Measurement of MUSE LSF

- Nonparametric 2D fits to arc lines in every slice, averaged to create a full-instrument LSF
- data: spectral line lamp exposures
- MUSE pipeline, Python scripts
- Linear and logarithmic wavelength scales

Comparison of MUSE LSF determinations

MUSE: importance of LSF for sky subtraction residuals

Sky emission line subtraction study

- simulated datacube MUSE with INM
- OH line intensity from theoretical model, [O I], Na I, O₂ from empirical data
- LSF expanded in hermitean gaussians:

$$LSF(x) = e^{-\frac{x^2}{2w^2}} + e^{-\frac{x^2}{w^2}} \cdot \sum_{i=3}^6 k_i H_i \left(\frac{x}{w} \right)$$

- lines fitted
- continuum fitted
- evaluation of residuals

MUSE: importance of LSF for sky subtraction residuals

systematic errors for OH 7-3 emission line region

statistical errors for OH 7-3 emission line region

MUSE: importance of LSF for sky subtraction residuals

End-to-end LSF simulation and fiber stability effects

Far Field Light Distribution – Stress Test

undisturbed fiber

bending

undisturbed fiber

Schmoll et al. 2003

End-to-end LSF simulation and fiber stability effects

546 nm

365 nm

852 nm

436 nm

644 nm

0°

3.5°

4.9°

6.0°

End-to-end simulation of fiber stability effects

(a) weighted pupil illumination

(b) spot diagram traces weights

(c) generate PSF from weighted spot

(d) convolve fibre near field with PSF

(e) extract „spectrum“

(f) find residuals for different weights

Near field / far field simulations of MMF

- Output field distribution of optical fibres is the input field of the spectrograph
 - Effects of the fibre translate into the illumination of the spectrograph pupil and into image plane

- Finite Element Method Simulations (FemSIM): **Rsoft** software as a mode solver
 - Design Fibre: Geometry, λ , N.A.
 - Maximum propagation modes $\Psi_m(x,y)$ calculated: 703
 - Calculate effective refractive index of each mode $n_{\text{eff},m}$
- Eigenmode Expansion Method (**EEM**): Calculation of electromagnetic propagation, representing the field in terms of a basis set of local modes.

A universal comb

10 December 2014. Scientists from the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics in Potsdam (AIP) and the Centre for innovation competence innoFSPEC have tested a novel optical frequency comb using an astronomical instrument. This new light source will improve the calibration of spectrographs and hence their scientific measurements.

« MARCH 2015 »						
Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
						1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	10	11	12	13	14	15

Selected spectrum.

"The special quality of the light generated by the optical frequency comb is that it consists of individual, discrete colours, with a precise frequency spacing," explains the

responsible innoFSPEC scientist Jose Boger. The superposition of laser light with two different frequencies in the spectrum is not continuous, as in a rainbow, but consists of lines with fixed spacing and dark gaps between them.

To analyse the light from stars and galaxies, scientists use a known light source. "The frequency comb provides a much more regular and regular, than the light from conventional sources," explains astrophysicist Andreas Kelz. "Thanks to this, we can measure the rotational speeds of galaxies or the chemical composition of stars more precisely."

After development in the laboratories of [innoFSPEC](#) Potsdam, the frequency comb was used during a recent observing campaign at the [Calar Alto Observatory](#) in southern Spain, which is equipped with the frequency comb. After the successful outcome of these tests, Roggeberg and his group, is sure that laser frequency combs will set new standards in astronomical precision.

innoFSPEC Laser Frequency Comb

- four-wave-mixing
- three nonlinear stages:
 - A+B:** generation of low-noise ultrashort pulses ($< 100\text{ fs}$)
 - C:** spectral broadening

Astrocomb
on-sky test
at Calar Alto

Summary

- (1) IFUs have a unique capability for spectrophotometry
- (2) Accurate flatfield correction for IFUs is difficult
- (3) MUSE flatfields affected by thermal effects
→ attached flatfield calibration helps
- (4) LSF varies over FoV and λ
- (5) LSF depends sensitively on optical light path, i.e. calibration light should mimic as closely as possible the illumination from the sky
- (6) Knowledge of LSF critical for accurate sky emission line subtraction

Nod-Shuffle Spectroscopy

1994A&A...281..603C

Astron. Astrophys. 281, 603–612 (1994)

ASTRONOMY
AND
ASTROPHYSICS

“Va-et-Vient” spectroscopy: a new mode for faint object CCD spectroscopy with very large telescopes[★]

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Received May 3, accepted August 3, 1993

Nod-Shuffle Spectroscopy

Glazebrook & Bland-Hawthorn 2001
PASP 113, 197

Nod- Shuffle Spectroscopy

Roth, M.M., Fechner, T., Wolter, D., Kelz, A., & Becker, T. 2002, *Experimental Astronomy*, 14, 99

MOSAIC

Nod-Shuffle Spectroscopy - applicable to ELT-MOS ?

